

Heterocyclic System III¹. Conversion of Semicarbazones, N-Benzoylhydrazones and *p*-Nitrophenylhydrazones of 4-Oxo-4*H*-[1] Benzopyran-3-Carboxaldehydes to the Pyrazole System.

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The semicarbazones (III), N-benzoylhydrazones (IV) and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazones (V) of 4-Oxo-4*H*-[1] benzopyran-3-carboxaldehydes undergo rearrangement on being refluxed in ethylene glycol, the former two yielding 4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles (VI) identical with the reaction products of hydrazine and the aforementioned carboxaldehydes, and the latter giving rise to 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles (VIII).

HYDRAZINE reacts with 4-Oxo-4*H*[1] benzopyran-3-carboxaldehydes (henceforth called as 3-formylchromones) to give directly 4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles (VI)², the intermediate hydrazones (I) not being isolable. Phenylhydrazones (II) of 3-formylchromones on being refluxed in either ethanolic potassium hydroxide³ or acetic acid¹ furnish 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles (VII). When refluxed in acetic acid, the hydrazones (II) undergo intramolecular nucleophilic attack at C-2 of the chromone moiety with concomitant opening of the pyrone ring so that the pyrazoles (VII) result in¹. It was our interest to see whether this type of intramolecular nucleophilic attack is possible for the hydrazones (III-V) having hydrazino group of much weaker nucleophilicity. Successful conversion of the hydrazones (III-V) to the pyrazole system is reported herein.

By refluxing a solution in glacial acetic acid, no change could be brought about in any of the hydrazones (III-V). In the rearrangements of the phenylhydrazones of α - β unsaturated carbonyl compounds to pyrazolines, to which the cyclisation reaction envisaged by us has formal analogy, it is uncertain to what extent the solubilities of the hydrazones influence the reaction⁴. It is anticipated that thermal energy rather than solubility mostly influences the aforementioned rearrangement. Our anticipation was proved to be correct when by refluxing in ethylene glycol (b. p. 200°) all the hydrazones (III-V) were converted to the pyrazole system.

The semicarbazones (III) when refluxed in ethylene glycol underwent rearrangement accompanied by hydrolytic removal of 1-carboxamido group to afford in 40-70% yield the same 4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles (VI) as were obtained by reacting the proper 3-formylchromones with hydrazine. It may be noted that hydrolytic removal of 1-carboxamido group is often observed in the cyclisation reaction of the semicarbazones of α - β unsaturated aldehydes or ketones to pyrazolines⁵. The N-benzoylhydrazones (IV) on similar treatment also rearranged to the pyrazoles (VI) (yield 40-60%), the benzoyl group being knocked off. It would not be irrelevant to mention here that ethylene glycol-*p*-toluenesulfonic acid mixture can cause even aromatic deacetylation⁶. The *p*-nitrophenylhydrazones (V) on being refluxed in ethylene glycol produced 4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles (VIII) in 50-80% yield, the latter on oxidation with chromic acid giving 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)pyrazole-4-carboxylic acid⁷. The different hydrazones (III-V) that were converted to the pyrazoles (VI and VIII) are shown in Table 1.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Elemental (C, H and N) analyses done for all the pyrazoles (VI and VIII), were in good agreement with the calculated values.

General method for the preparation of the hydrazones(III-V)

The semicarbazones(III) were prepared by adding a warm solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.55 g, 0.005 mole) and sodium acetate (1.0 g) in water (2-3 ml) to a hot solution of the properly substituted 3-formylchromones^{8,9} (0.005 mole) in ethanol(3-5 ml). N-Benzoylhydrazones(IV) and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazones(V) were prepared by refluxing 3-formylchromones in ethanol with equimolar amounts of benzoic hydrazide and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine respectively.

TABLE 1—MELTING POINTS OF DIFFERENT HYDRAZONES (III-V)^a AND THEIR REARRANGED PRODUCTS (VI AND VIII)^b

Substituent X	Hydrazones (III)	Hydrazones (IV)	Pyrazoles (VI) obtd. from (III) and (IV)	Acetates ^c of (VI)	Hydrazones (V)	Pyrazoles (VIII) obtd. from (V)	Acetates ^d of pyrazoles (VIII)
H	240	207-8	124	115	248-50	188	150
CH ₃	257-8	—	170	—	260	185	157
Cl	250	209	180	97	255	187	151
Br	230	222	170	112	252	190	158
NO ₂	228	225	213	242-3	262	238	171

^aThe hydrazones (III-V) whenever recrystallised, were recrystallised from acetic acid.

^bRecrystallised from ethanol or aqueous ethanol.

^cAll these acetates were recrystallised from benzene-pet. ether, and were characterised from their NMR spectra, the three protons of O—Ac coming as singlet at, say δ 2.25 and those of N—Ac appearing at δ 2.70 (singlet).

^dRecrystallised from chloroform-pet. ether.

4-(2-Hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (VI, X=H) from chromone-3-carboxaldehydesemicarbazone (III, X=H).

The semicarbazone (III, X=H) (0.70 g) was refluxed in ethylene glycol (10 ml) for 6 hr, cooled and diluted with water. The precipitated solid was filtered and crystallised from acetone-water (charcoal) to afford the pyrazole (VI, X=H) (0.54 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 124°, v_{max} (CHCl₃) 3220 (w, br, NH), 3140 (w, br, OH chelated with carbonyl), 1622 (s, aryl pyrazolyl ketone chelated with OH). When refluxed with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate it gave a mixture of a monoacetate and a diacetate that were separated by fractional crystallisation from chloroform, the monoacetate precipitating out first as colorless crystals, m.p. 164°, τ (CDCl₃) 1.63 (s, 1H, pyrazole H₃), 2.00 (s, 1H, pyrazole H₅), 2.43-2.99 (m, 5H, ArH and NH) and 7.83 (s, 3H, -O-COCH₃). The diacetate had m.p. 115° (benzene-pet. ether) and showed NMR signals at τ (CDCl₃) 1.55 (s, 1H, pyrazole H₃), 2.00 (s, 1H, pyrazole H₅), 2.27-2.97 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.28 (s, 3H, -N-COCH₃) and 7.80 (s, 3H, -O.COCH₃). For all other pyrazoles (VI) only the diacetates were obtained (Table 1).

Authentic sample of 4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (VI, X=H)

To a hot ethanolic solution of 3-formylchromone (0.878 g, 0.005 mole) was added an aqueous solution of hydrazine prepared from hydrazine hydrochloride (0.52g, 0.005 mole) and sodium acetate (1.0 g), and the mixture warmed for 15 min, then it was cooled and diluted with water when the pyrazole (VI, X=H) (0.85 g), m.p. 122° was obtained.

All other semicarbazones (III) (Table 1) were similarly converted to the respective pyrazoles (VI), the identity of the latter being also confirmed by their independent synthesis from proper 3-formylchromones and hydrazine as described above.

Rearrangement of N-benzoylhydrazone (IV, X=H)

By refluxing a mixture of 3-formylchromone (0.35 g, 0.002 mole) and benzoic hydrazide (0.27 g, 0.002 mole), m.p. 75-80° was obtained the hydrazone (IV, X=H) (0.56 g), m.p. 207-208°, v_{max} (KBr): 3425 (s, br, NH), 1645 (s, CONH- and -CH=N-) and 1625 cm⁻¹ (pyrone carbonyl and -C=C-) (Found: C, 69.43; H, 4.32; N, 9.54; Calc. for C₁₇H₁₂N₂O₃: C, 69.52; H, 4.10; N, 9.59%). This hydrazone (0.56g) on being refluxed in ethylene glycol afforded 4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (0.29 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 124°. All other hydrazones (IV) were similarly rearranged to the pyrazoles (VI).

1-(p-Nitrophenyl)-4-(2-hydroxy-5-bromobenzoyl)pyrazole (VIII, X=Br).

The experimental procedure for the cyclisation of the nitrophenylhydrazone (V, X=Br) to the pyrazole (VIII, X=Br) is described here as a representative case. A solution of the nitrophenylhydrazone (V, X=Br) (0.30 g) in ethylene glycol (10 ml) was refluxed for 8 hr, then cooled and diluted with water when the pyrazole (VIII, X=Br) (0.22 g), m.p. 190° (ethanol) was obtained. It showed IR absorption at 3115 (m, OH chelated with carbonyl), 1620 (s, diarylketone chelated with OH), and 1590 cm⁻¹ (s, -C=N- and aromatic) in addition to two strong absorption bands at 1542 and 1332 cm⁻¹ due to aromatic nitro group. Its acetate showed absorption peaks at 1757 (ester carbonyl), 1650 (keto-carbonyl), 1590 (-C=N- and aromatic), 1545 and 1332 (aromatic NO₂).

Oxidation of the pyrazoles (VIII)

Each of the pyrazoles (VIII) was oxidised with chromic acid in acetic acid-water-acetone mixture¹ to afford 1-(p-nitrophenyl)pyrazole-4-carboxylic acid, m.p. 245-8° (CHCl₃) (lit⁷, m.p. 250°).

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